

Syntheses of 1,5-benzothiazepines. Part-XXXIX : Syntheses and antimicrobial studies of 8-substituted-2,5-dihydro-2-(furan-2-yl)-4-(2-hydroxyphenyl/4-methylphenyl)-1,5-benzothiazepines

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Manuscript received 20 September 2013, revised 09 October 2014, accepted 05 January 2015

Abstract : The syntheses of novel twelve 8-substituted-2,5-dihydro-2-(furan-2-yl)-4-(2-hydroxyphenyl/4-methylphenyl)-1,5-benzothiazepines have been carried out by the reactions of 5-substituted-2-aminobenzenethiols, the substituents being fluoro, chloro, bromo, methyl, methoxy or ethoxy, with the enolisable heterocyclic ketones, 3-(furan-2-yl)-1-(2-hydroxyphenyl/4-methylphenyl)-2-propenone in dry ethanol saturated with dry HCl; and characterized by analytical and spectral data comprising IR, ¹H NMR and mass spectral studies. On being screened for antimicrobial activity against the Gram-positive bacteria, *Staphylococcus aureus* and Gram-negative bacteria *Enterobacter cloacae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and fungus, *Candida albicans* in 36 h duration of incubation, it was found that the 2-(furan-2-yl)-2,5-dihydro-8-methoxy-4-(4-methylphenyl)-1,5-benzothiazepine displayed notable antibacterial activity, one and half times higher than that of Meropenem, against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and good antifungal activity against *Candida albicans* using Fluconazole as reference standard.

Keywords : Enolisable heterocyclic ketone, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Enterobacter cloacae*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, *Candida albicans*.

Introduction

1,5-Benzothiazepines having different heterocyclyl groups at positions 2, 3 and 4 have been reported to function as Ca²⁺ antagonist¹, anti-ulcer²⁻⁶, analgesic⁷, vasodepressant⁸, anti-hypertensive⁹, anti-amnesia and anti-dementia agent¹⁰, besides acting as insecticidal¹¹, anti-bacterial and antifungal¹²⁻¹⁶ agents. Several naturally occurring and synthetic 1,5-benzothiazepine derivatives having heterocyclic moiety are known to be associated with biological and pharmacological activities such as anti-inflammatory¹⁷, anti-implantation¹⁸, anticancer¹⁹⁻²¹, pesticidal²⁰, nematocidal²³, antiuterotropic²⁴, anticonvulsant²⁵ and CNS^{16,25} depressant activities. The applications of these derivatives are also extended to textile and paper industries²⁶.

In our earlier comparative studies on 1,5-benzothiazepines bearing phenyl/heterocyclic moieties, greater antifungal activity has been reported²⁷ in the compounds having the thienyl group, against *Candida albicans*. Besides, bicyclic 1,5-benzothiazepines having furanyl group

as a substituent have also been found to be useful for their antibacterial and antifungal activity²⁸.

Hence, the syntheses and antimicrobial studies of 8-substituted-2,5-dihydro-2-(furan-2-yl)-4-(2-hydroxyphenyl/4-methylphenyl)-1,5-benzothiazepines are being reported herein. All the synthesized compounds have been screened for antibacterial activity against the Gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* and the Gram-negative bacteria *Enterobacter cloacae* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, with Vancomycin, Cefoperazone/Sulbactam and Meropenem as reference drugs and antifungal activity against the fungus, *Candida albicans* with Fluconazole as the reference drug.

Results and discussion

5-Substituted-2-aminobenzenethiols²⁹, **4a-f**, and 3-(furan-2-yl)-1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-2-propenone³⁰, **3a** or 3-(furan-2-yl)-1-(4-methylphenyl)-2-propenone, **3b**, prepared by reacting equimolar quantities of furfuraldehyde, **1** with 4-methylacetophenone, **2b** in ethanol containing 10%

NaOH, were refluxed in equimolar quantities in dry ethanol saturated with dry hydrogen chloride for 11–13 h to obtain the twelve new title products, 8-substituted-2,5-dihydro-2-(furan-2-yl)-4-(2-hydroxyphenyl/4-methylphenyl)-1,5-benzothiazepines, **5a-l** in a single step in 54–63% yields (Table 1).

Table 1. Physical constants and micro analytical data of **5a-l**

Compd.	Mol. formula (Mol. wt.)	M.p. (°C)	R_f	Yield (%)
5a	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ FNO ₂ S (339)	87–88	0.74	56.28
5b	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ ClNO ₂ S (355)	79–81	0.65	52.31
5c	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ BrNO ₂ S (400)	88–89	0.78	57.10
5d	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ NO ₂ S (335)	95–96	0.82	55.11
5e	C ₂₀ H ₁₇ NO ₃ S (351)	85–86	0.56	55.12
5f	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ NO ₃ S (365)	90–92	0.60	63.01
5g	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ FNOS (337)	94–95	0.84	54.00
5h	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ ClNOS (353)	82–84	0.91	63.09
5i	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ BrNOS (398)	78–79	0.78	63.36
5j	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ NOS (333)	115–117	0.72	57.06
5k	C ₂₁ H ₁₉ NO ₂ S (349)	128–129	0.66	57.16
5l	C ₂₂ H ₂₁ NO ₂ S (363)	140–142	0.67	59.71

The acid catalyzed reaction of 5-substituted-2-aminobenzenethiols **4a-f** with the enolisable 3-(furan-2-yl)-1-(2-hydroxyphenyl/4-methylphenyl)-2-propenone **3**, is initiated by the nucleophilic attack of the lone pair of sulphhydryl electrons at the activated β -carbon atom of heterocyclic ketones, to give Michael adduct intermediates, which simultaneously undergo dehydrative cyclisation resulting into the formation of the final products, 8-substituted-2,5-dihydro-2-(furan-2-yl)-4-(2-hydroxyphenyl/4-methylphenyl)-1,5-benzothiazepines **5a-l**, in a single step (Scheme 1).

In the IR spectra of 3-(furan-2-yl)-1-(4-methylphenyl)-2-propenone **3b**, appearance of a band at around 1665 cm⁻¹ indicated that the carbonyl group is in conjugation with vinyl unsaturation and also, with phenyl group. The IR spectra of the final products **5a-l** showed a single absorption band in the region 3146–3136 cm⁻¹, which may be due to the presence of secondary amino group. The absence of characteristic absorptions for $\nu C=O$ and νNH_2 in the region 1690–1650 cm⁻¹ and 3450–3200 cm⁻¹ respectively, indicated that the reaction between 5-substituted-2-aminobenzenethiols and 3-(furan-2-yl)-1-aryl-2-propenones had taken place to give the final products in a single step. Absorption bands obtained at around 3018–3008, 1600–1590, 1548–1543 and 1458–1447 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to aromatic skeletal vibrations. The absorption at around 2920–2915 cm⁻¹ and 1385–1375 cm⁻¹ may be assigned to stretching and bending vibrations of aliphatic C-H absorptions respectively. The absorption bands in the region, 1280–1150 cm⁻¹ and at 1035–1030 cm⁻¹ in the compounds indicated the presence of $\nu C-O-C$ vibrations.

The ¹H NMR spectra of 3-(furan-2-yl)-1-(4-methylphenyl)-2-propenone, **3b** showed a singlet at δ 2.43 indicating the presence of methyl group. Two doublets, observed at around δ 6.51 and 6.71, may be assigned to the two protons at C-2 and C-3, respectively. The downfield position of these absorptions may be due to the presence of the carbonyl and furanyl groups. Multiplets at around δ 7.26–7.96, corresponding to seven aromatic protons, were also observed.

The ¹H NMR spectra of all the final products **5a-l** showed a doublet at δ 6.87–7.04 (1H, d, J 7 Hz), which may be assigned to C-2 proton and another doublet at δ 7.84–7.97 (1H, d, J 7 Hz) may be assigned to the proton at C-3. A broad singlet of one proton absorption at around δ 4.10–4.12 may be due to secondary amino proton. These observations indicate the formation of the enamino 2,5-dihydro form **5a-l(i)**, instead of the tautomeric 2,3-dihydro imino form **5a-l(ii)**. Absorption peaks, observed as multiplets in the region δ 6.91–7.93, are assigned to the aromatic protons. Singlets at around δ 2.39–2.43, integrating for three protons each, may be assigned to the methyl protons, in the spectra of **5d** and **5g-l**. Another three proton singlet, corresponding to the methyl group at po-

Note

Scheme 1

sition-8, was obtained at δ 2.43 in the spectrum of **5j**. A singlet of three protons at δ 3.85, due to methoxyl group was observed in compound **5e** and **5k**. Absorption as a triplet at δ 1.46 (3H, t, J 7 Hz) and a quartet at δ 4.10 (2H, q, J 7 Hz) may be assigned to methyl and methylene protons of ethoxyl group in compound **5f** and **5l** (Table 2).

In the ¹³C NMR analyses of the compounds **5d**, **5e**, **5j** and **5k**, absorption signals around δ 113, 117 and 118, which may be assigned to C-2, C-7, C-9 respectively were observed. Absorption signals near δ 136.5 and 125 may be assigned to C-4 and C-3; and δ 132, and 120 due

to C-5a and C-9a respectively, while those around δ 151 and 142 to C-2', C-5', respectively, due to the presence of electronegative oxygen atom at alpha position; other peaks in the region δ 104–130 of the spectra may correspond to the six remaining aromatic carbons attached to C-2 and C-4. In the spectra of the compounds **5d** and **5e**, carbon signals were observed at δ 21.7 and 55.8 due to CH₃ and OCH₃ at position-8. **5j** showed signals at δ 21.9 and 21.8 due to the two methyl group carbons at C-8 and C-4''; while **5k** showed a signal at δ 55.6 due to OCH₃ group at C-8 in addition to the C-4'' signal at 21.65 of the methyl group.

Table 2. Characteristic ^1H NMR data (CDCl_3 , δ values in ppm, J in Hz) of **5a-l**

Compd.	NH (1H, br)	CH_3 (3H, s)	$\text{C}_2\text{-H}$ (1H, d, J 8 Hz)	$\text{C}_3\text{-H}$ (1H, d, J 8 Hz)	$\text{C}_8\text{-XH}$	Aromatic proton (11H, m)
5a	4.11	–	6.80	7.95	–	6.98–7.89
5b	4.12	–	6.79	7.93	–	6.97–7.87
5c	4.09	–	6.74	7.96	–	7.00–7.88
5d	4.11	–	6.54	7.97	2.40 (3H, s)	6.55–7.93
5e	4.10	–	6.77	7.93	3.85 (3H, s)	6.79–7.66
5f	4.12	–	6.77	7.93	1.46 (3H, t, J 7), 4.11 (2H, q, J 7)	6.77–7.90
5g	4.10	2.42	6.92	7.96	–	6.93–7.87
5h	4.12	2.41	6.87	7.95	–	6.91–7.89
5i	4.10	2.43	6.91	7.84	–	7.02–7.82
5j	4.12	2.39	6.95	7.94	2.43 (3H, s)	7.03–7.86
5k	4.12	2.43	6.93	7.92	3.85 (3H, s)	7.25–7.80
5l	4.11	2.40	7.04	7.97	1.46 (3H, t, J 7), 4.10 (2H, q, J 7)	7.05–7.93

The mass spectra of **5b**, showed cluster of the molecular ion peaks, m/z , $[\text{M}]^+$, $[\text{M}+2]^+$ and $[\text{M}+4]^+$ at 355, 357 and 359 respectively and compound **5h** showed cluster of molecular ion peaks, $[\text{M}]^+$, $[\text{M}+2]^+$ at m/z , 353 and 355 which correspond to the molecular mass of the product, whereas that of **5c** showed molecular ion peaks, m/z , $[\text{M}]^+$ and $[\text{M}+2]^+$ at 400 and 402 and **5i** showed molecular ion peaks, m/z , at 398 and 400. The intensities of $[\text{M}+2]^+$ peaks indicated the presence of chlorine and bromine in **5c** and **5i**, respectively. The results of elemental analyses were found to be satisfactory, being within the permissible limits of error.

Antimicrobial activity :

All the synthesized compounds were screened for their antibacterial activity against the Gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus* and the Gram-negative bacteria *Enterobacter cloacae* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, with Vancomycin, Cefoperazone/Sulbactam and Meropenem as reference drugs, respectively and for antifungal activity against the fungus, *Candida albicans* with Fluconazole as reference drug. The paper disc method³¹ was used at the concentration of 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{disc}$.

Most of the synthesized compounds, **5a-l** were found to show good antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*; while moderate activity was shown against

Enterobacter cloacae and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Compound 8-chloro-2-(furan-2-yl)-2,5-dihydro-4-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-1,5-benzothiazepine, **5b** showed almost one and half times greater activity relative to Vancomycin against the Gram-positive bacteria, *Staphylococcus aureus*. Compounds **5f**, **5h**, and **5k** also showed good relative activity (activity index = 1.08) and compound **5i** showed activity equal to that of the reference compound.

Against *Enterobacter cloacae*, compound **5i** was found to show relative activity equal to that of Cefoperazone/Sulbactam, the reference compound; while 2-(furan-2-yl)-2,5-dihydro-8-methoxy-4-(4-methylphenyl)-1,5-benzothiazepine, **5k** was found to show one and half times higher activity than the reference standard Meropenem, against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*.

The 8-chloro derivatives, **5b** and **5h**; and 8-alkoxy derivatives, **5e**, **5f**, **5k**, **5l** were found to show good activity (activity index = 0.92–1.21) against the fungus, *Candida albicans*, as compared to reference standard compound, Fluconazole.

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected. TLC was used for checking homogeneity of the compounds, using benzene : ethanol : aq. ammonia (50%) in the ratio 7 : 2 : 1 as solvent system. The IR spectra were taken in KBr

Note

Table 3. Antimicrobial activity of **5a-l**

Compd.	Bacteria			Fungus
	Gram-positive	Gram-negative		<i>Candida albicans</i>
	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Enterobacter cloacae</i>	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>	
5a	9 (0.75)	12 (0.70)	10 (0.71)	–
5b	17 (1.41)	14 (0.82)	12 (0.85)	13 (0.92)
5c	10 (0.83)	11 (0.64)	8 (0.57)	14 (1.00)
5d	–	15 (0.88)	17 (1.21)	10 (0.71)
5e	11 (0.91)	–	10 (0.71)	15 (1.07)
5f	13 (1.08)	11 (0.64)	17 (1.21)	16 (1.14)
5g	–	–	12 (0.85)	11 (0.78)
5h	13 (1.08)	16 (0.94)	14 (0.82)	16 (1.14)
5i	12 (1.00)	17 (1.00)	10 (0.71)	13 (0.92)
5j	–	13 (0.76)	–	12 (0.85)
5k	13 (1.08)	12 (0.70)	21 (1.50)	17 (1.21)
5l	11 (0.91)	14 (0.82)	10 (0.71)	15 (1.07)

Values in parentheses represent activity index.

Zone of inhibition of Vancomycin for *Staphylococcus aureus* is 12 mm, Cefoperazone/Sulbactam for *Enterobacter cloacae* is 17 mm, Meropenem for *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* is 14 mm and Fluconazole for *Candida albicans* is 14 mm.

pellets on a Perkin-Elmer RX1 FT IR spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker DRX-300 (300 MHz FT NMR with low and high temperature facility), TMS was used as internal standard and CDCl₃ as solvent. The FAB mass spectra were recorded on JEOL-SX 102/DA-600 Mass spectrometer/Data system using Argon/Xenon (6 kV, 10 mA) as the FAB gas. The accelerating voltage was 10 kV and spectra were recorded at room temperature. *m*-Nitrobenzoyl alcohol (NBA) was used as the matrix. Microestimations for C, H, N and S were carried out in Elemental Analyzer, Carlo Erba 1108. The spectral analyses and elemental analyses were car-

ried out at the Sophisticated Analytical Instrumentation Facility, Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow. Antimicrobial activity was carried out at Microbiology Department, S.M.S. Medical College, Jaipur.

Six 5-substituted-2-amino-benzenethiols³⁰ and 3-(furan-2-yl)-1-(2-hydroxyphenyl)-2-propenone³¹, **3a**, were prepared by literature reported methods.

3-(Furan-2-yl)-1-(4-methylphenyl)-2-propenone (3b) :

Equimolar quantities of furfuraldehyde (**1**; 0.01 mol, 1.36 g) and 4-methoxyacetophenone (**2**; 0.01 mol, 1.34 g) were taken in dry ethanol separately and mixed with stirring by keeping them in ice-bath. 10% NaOH solution was added to this mixture till the color changed to light brown. Vigorous stirring was continued for an additional half an hour, when the greenish white colored suspension solution was obtained. On refrigerating the mixture over night, the crude was obtained, which was filtered, dried and crystallized from dry methanol to give finally greenish white colored crystals of 3-(furan-2-yl)-1-(4-methylphenyl)-2-propenone [**3**, m.p. 54.5–55.5 °C; yield, 1.62 g (76.85%), *R_f* 0.87, IR (KBr) : 3000 (Ar C-H), 2955 (Aliphatic C-H), 1665 (C=C=O), 1570, 1520, 1455 (Ar skeletal); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ : 6.51 (1H, d, C₂-H), 6.71 (1H, d, C₃-H), 2.43 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.26–7.96 (7H, m, aromatic H).

2-(Furan-2-yl)-2,5-dihydro-8-methoxy-4-(4-methylphenyl)-1,5-benzothiazepine (5k) :

The reaction mixture of 2-amino-5-methoxybenzenethiol (**4e**; 0.155 g, 0.001 mol) and 3-(furan-2-yl)-1-(4-methylphenyl)-2-propenone (**3**; 0.001 mol, 0.212 g) in dry ethanol (10 ml), saturated with dry hydrogen chloride, was refluxed for 11 h, till color changed from light yellow to deep brown. Excess of the solvent was removed under reduced pressure to obtain the crude, which was crystallized from ethanol to obtain 2-(furan-2-yl)-2,5-dihydro-8-methoxy-4-(4-methylphenyl)-1,5-benzothiazepine [**5k**, m.p. 128–129 °C; yield, 0.199 g (57.16%), *R_f* 0.66, IR (KBr) : 3143 (NH); 1275 cm⁻¹ (C-O-C); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ : 3.85 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.93 (1H, d, C₂-H, *J* 8 Hz), 7.92 (1H, d, C₃-H, *J* 8 Hz), 2.43 (3H, s, CH₃), 7.25–7.80 (10H, m, aromatic H), 4.12 (1H, br, NH); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃) δ : 21.65 (CH₃ on C-4'), 55.6 (OCH₃ on C-8), 113.4 (C-2), 117.3 (C-7), 118.2 (C-9), 122.4 (C-9a), 124.8 (C-3), 131.9 (C-5a), 136.9

(C-4), 142.6 (C-5'), 151.2 (C-8), 152.5 (C-2')].

Compounds **5a-j** and **5l** were prepared by using similar procedures. Their physical constants and spectral data are given in Tables 1 and 2.

Acknowledgement

The authors gratefully acknowledge the financial assistance provided by the CSIR, New Delhi and providing JRF/SRF to Rajkumari Jadon. Thanks are also due to Principal, L.B.S. Government P.G. College, Kotputli, Jaipur, and Principal, SMS Medical College, Jaipur for providing the facility to work and the Sophisticated Analytical Instrument Facility (SAIF), Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow for providing the elemental analyses and spectral data.

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